

A MODEL FOR THE BEHAVIOUR OF THICK COMPOSITE LAMINATES IN HYDROCARBON FIRES

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SUMMARY: A model for the fire behaviour of thick composite laminates in hydrocarbon fires has been developed and experimentally validated by furnace fire testing. The integrity of certain composite materials in the form of thick laminates under severe fire conditions is demonstrated to be surprisingly good. Heat transfer through the laminate is slow in comparison to metallic materials which leads to long survival times and containment of the fire. The endothermic decomposition of the matrix provides the basic mechanism for slowing down the heat transfer through composite laminates, whilst the overall integrity of the structure is maintained for considerable time due to the non-combustible reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: fire behaviour, structural integrity, fire testing, cone calorimeter, ablation, offshore, modelling

INTRODUCTION

In almost every application for composites the issue of material response to fire is one which must be addressed. Of course, whenever a potentially combustible organic matrix is present the resultant hazards due to heat release, smoke and toxicity must be taken into account: a comprehensive range of standard test procedures is available to characterise behaviour and the composites industry has applied these responsibly for many years. In the past the question of combustibility has prevented the application of composite materials in fire-sensitive areas, but with the adoption of performance-led design procedures, composites are finding increasing application in new structures. Aside from the combustibility issue, it must be recognised that exceptional structural integrity can be achieved in certain types of composite structures under fire conditions. The combination of low thermal conductivity, resin endotherm effects and structural integrity combine to provide excellent fire characteristics for application as structural members, fire walls, blast panels and passive fire protection systems.

The main thrust of this paper concerns the use of composite materials in large engineering structures and their integrity when subjected to fire. Research carried out to support the use of these materials in the offshore industry shows that in the correct circumstances the fire integrity of large composite structures can be superior to that of their steel counterparts.

USE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS OFFSHORE

Markets for composites of all types (glass, aramid, carbon fibre) in large scale engineering structures are expected to increase considerably in the future. The most promising materials, for cost reasons are glass reinforced plastics (GRP), which are now entering the offshore industry in a range of areas where their lightness and corrosion resistance can be used to special advantage. The authors are principally involved in research related to the offshore industry [1], but clearly many of the issues raised here will relate to other industries involving processing and large scale structures. The most important factor in composites gaining access to the offshore industry has been the recent move away from prescriptive regulations requiring non-combustibility towards a *performance-based* approach to design- a change which is also taking place in other industries.

Two important application areas have led the use of GRP offshore. The first is pipework for aqueous liquids (especially seawater for fire-water distribution mains) [2]. In these applications glass reinforced epoxy (GRE) pipework has been shown to have a lower through-life cost than competing metallic systems, which include duplex stainless steel, Inconel and even titanium. It has been well-known for some time that liquid-filled composite pipes and tanks show excellent resistance to fire. In those cases where pipes under threat may not contain liquid they can, of course, be protected by conventional passive fire protection materials. Comprehensive performance-based guidelines for GRE pipes, issued by the UK Offshore Operators Association [3] have significantly accelerated these applications.

The other significant application is in panelling for both floors and walls. The first major tonnage on a North Sea platform involved fire protection panels for the helideck of the Amerada Hess Rob Roy rig, which was deployed in the 1980s. It is interesting to note that, despite their perceived combustibility, all the early uses of GRP offshore involved applications where fire was an important issue. Offshore applications of composites have been discussed in several recent publications, including references [4] and [5].

STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS VS. PERCEIVED HAZARDS

The key factors in relation to fire hazard are; smoke and toxicity, ignitability/spread of flame, heat release and structural integrity. These factors assume different degrees of importance, depending upon the engineering application area. In enclosed locations for instance, where personnel may be present, smoke and toxicity, which determine ease of escape and survivability are of paramount importance. Ignitability, spread of flame and heat release, on the other hand, are important in determining the development of a fire when there is a risk of ignition from some other source, such as an electrical fault or some other defined fire hazard. Heat release from the composite material may or may not be important, depending on the overall load of combustible material present. In offshore plant, for instance, when the main hazard is a hydrocarbon fire from a large quantity of stored oil or gas, heat release from the composite materials present may not be of great significance.

Structural integrity is the most important issue when a composite structure is required to retain its function for a period of time during fire exposure. This applies in several structural and semi-structural applications, as in the cases of composite pipework or pultruded gratings and handrails. It will be shown that the most significant factor in maintaining integrity and in preventing the transmission of heat through the structure is the *slow burn-through* effect,

which can be observed in many types of composite, provided the section is of sufficient thickness (usually above about 9mm). Because of the ability of composites to limit heat transmission they are beginning to be used in roles involving passive fire protection, such as in the protection of steel jacket structures and risers offshore.

QUANTIFYING THE FIRE RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

A range of different fire performance requirements may apply, depending on the application and environment. There is a similarly broad range of standard tests [6], which may be used to quantify the response of the material. Two major test procedures are the oxygen consumption calorimeter and the furnace fire test. The NBS Cone Calorimeter [7], provides an accurate method of measuring heat release and combustion products in a fire.

Figure 1 Comparison of the main resin systems used in composite engineering structures. Cone calorimeter results and the overall toxicity index according to standard test procedures are plotted using polyester as the baseline. The composite systems are: isophthalic polyester (Freemans Stypol 73/2785), amine-cured epoxy (Araldite LY1927 HY1927), vinyl ester (Freemans Stypol Atlac 580/05) and phenolic (BP Cellobond J2018/L Phencat 10) 50% w/w glass woven roving laminates. Specimen thickness 6mm. For the cone calorimeter test average values obtained for an irradiance of 50 kw/m² are plotted.

A comparison of the heat release and toxicity of the different matrix systems carried out using standard test procedures is shown in Figure. 1. The baseline is isophthalic polyester. The lower heat release and smoke emission of the phenolic laminates is evident. An increased yield of carbon monoxide is observed for phenolic but the overall toxicity index remains lower than competing resins. Clearly there are strong arguments for the use of phenolic systems in the most personnel-sensitive areas.

Figure 2 shows total heat release values (expressed per unit volume of composite) measured by cone calorimetry, plotted against laminate thickness. All the materials show a thickness effect: the effective heat release falls considerably as the laminate thickness increases, suggesting that composites will perform well when used in thick sections.

Figure 2 Total heat release per unit volume as a function of laminate thickness. The specimen details are identical to those in Figure 1.

FURNACE TESTS

Furnace tests are used to measure the structural integrity of composites in fires [6]. Experimental fire tests were carried out using a purpose built furnace with an active volume of 3.375 cubic metres, fired by a single portable burner.

Figure 3 Laminated panel response to hydrocarbon curve furnace fire tests ranked as a Relative Fire Barrier Performance Index. The ranking is the time required for the cold face to reach 160°C normalised with reference to standard polyester glass woven roving laminates.

The test panels were mounted vertically in a specially designed frame forming the door of the furnace. For the purposes of model validation the furnace temperature was programmed to

follow the hydrocarbon fire curve and the fire resistance of the material tested conventionally expressed as the time taken for the cold face of the panel to reach a temperature of 160°C. Experimental relative fire barrier performance data derived from hydrocarbon curve furnace fire testing is shown in Figure 3. The standard development material has been taken as isophthalic polyester / glass woven roving with a glass volume fraction of 55%. The most successful materials in terms of thermal barrier performance are those with the highest endothermic contribution. For panels with an aramid content the reinforcement also decomposes endothermically this is illustrated by the advantageous thermal barrier performance observed in Figure 3, especially when aramid is combined with glass reinforcement for added structural integrity.

In the furnace fire tests the panel cold face is exposed to stationary air, which removes very little heat. If heat is actually removed from one side of the laminate the time to failure can be even further prolonged. This effect can usefully be employed with composite pipework containing a stationary, or better still, flowing fluid, and is one of the reasons why GRE pipes have begun to be so widely-used for offshore fire-water systems.

MODELLING THE MATERIAL RESPONSE TO HYDROCARBON FIRE

The factors which contribute to the slow burn-through effect in composites are thermal conduction through the laminate, transport properties of the residual reinforcement (and carbonaceous char, if present), the endotherm due to resin decomposition and the mass flux or convection of volatiles away from the hot surface.

A thermal model [8], taking into account the decomposition processes mentioned above has been developed to assist in the prediction of fire integrity. This model, based on previously reported models for ablative behaviour [9-11] may be used with a range of different boundary conditions and has been validated by tests on laminates of different thickness'. The basic governing equation expressed in one dimension is of the form:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + M_G \frac{\partial}{\partial x} h_G - \rho A e^{-\frac{E}{RT}} (Q_p - h_c + h_G) \quad (1)$$

where:

- T , t and x are temperature, time and through-thickness coordinate, respectively
- ρ , C_p and k are the density, specific heat and conductivity of the composite
- M_G is the mass flux of volatiles from decomposition
- h_A and h_G are the respective enthalpies of the composite and evolved gas
- Q_p is the endothermic decomposition energy
- A , E and R are the rate constants for the decomposition reaction and the gas constant.

The three terms on the right hand side of equation (1) relate to heat conduction, volatile convection and endothermic resin decomposition, respectively. Modelling of the thermal conductivity and specific heat as the composite is ablated is described fully in reference [12]. The rate constants for the decomposition term are estimated from thermo-gravimetric measurements on laminate samples.

Figure 4 Experimental hydrocarbon curve furnace fire tests results (solid lines) for isophthalic polyester / glass woven roving laminated panels and corresponding one-dimensional modelled response (dotted lines). Intermediate curves are inter-laminar temperatures

Figure 4 shows furnace test results from a range different thickness polyester/glass laminated panels, used to confirm the model constants, demonstrating that good correlation can be obtained between experiment and model over a wide range of laminate thickness'.

Figure 5 A comparison of the calculated temperature response of a 25mm polyester / glass laminate with (dotted lines) and without (solid lines) the decomposition term.

Comparison of the significance of the terms on the right of equation (1) shows that the most important factor in the slow burn-through effect is not the low conductivity of the composite laminate but the highly endothermic nature of the resin decomposition reaction. This is illustrated in Figure 5 which compares the calculated temperature distribution with and without the decomposition term. The heat absorbed by resin decomposition is the most

important factor limiting the rate of ablation of the laminate and in preventing the transmission of heat through the specimen to the cold face. In fact the decomposition model outlined above is based on an ablative model originally developed to describe the behaviour of wood in fires [10].

The kinetics of the decomposition reaction during a hydrocarbon fire test are illustrated in Figure 6. The rate parameters, A and E, in equation 1 are obtained experimentally by thermo-gravimetric analysis at a fixed heating rate (solid curve Figure. 6(a)). The dotted lines in Figure 6(a) are the calculated resin decomposition curves through the laminate thickness for the variable heating rates applied during a hydrocarbon curve fire test. The differences between the experimental and calculated TGA curves are due to the variation of heating rates during a hydrocarbon fire test.

Figure 6 (a) Comparison of experimental thermo-gravimetric data collected at 25°C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere (solid line) with the calculated mass loss at points through the laminate thickness (dotted lines). (b) The calculated effective heating rates for a polyester / glass laminate during a hydrocarbon curve fire test. The highest rate is at the surface, decreasing at points through the thickness.

The calculated variation of the effective heating rate during a hydrocarbon curve fire test is plotted in Figure 6(b) for through thickness positions in an 11mm thick polyester / glass panel. The highest heating rate is at the hot face as expected and the test is predicted to have reached a steady state after ≈16 minutes.

APPLICATIONS OF THE THERMAL MODEL

The thermal model may be used to provide design information for the use of composite materials in fire sensitive applications. Design charts prepared using the validated computer model are shown in Figure. 8. Figure. 8a allows polyester woven roving laminate thickness' to be defined by the allowed cold face temperature rise in a hydrocarbon fire, while Figure. 8b shows the cold face response of laminates to a predetermined heat flux.

Figure 7 Design charts for polyester glass WR laminates prepared using the thermal model.
 (a) Hydrocarbon curve fire response - thickness required for specified temperature.
 (b) Cold face temperature response for specified incident heat flux vs. Thickness.

The application of composite materials as passive fire protection requires a prediction of the lifetime during a fire. Steel retains its structural properties up to about 500°C but, because of its relatively high thermal conductivity structures tend to reach this temperature quite quickly in fires. For this reason, metallic structures subject to fire hazards need to be protected, usually by an intumescent or other passive heat protection medium. Composite structures, by contrast, transmit heat less rapidly and will often maintain their integrity for longer. Composite materials are increasingly applied in offshore structures as structural members, risers and combined corrosion/fire protection in the splash zone. An example of the use of polyester/glass cladding as passive fire protection offshore is shown in Figure. 8. A steel tubular clad in 30mm polyester/glass is shown in Figure. 8a and the predicted temperature response of the cylindrical section to a hydrocarbon fire is shown in Figure. 8 b. The steel temperature remains below 160°C for more than 60 minutes satisfying design requirements.

a.

b.

Figure 8 (a) Polyester / glass passive fire protection applied to a steel riser. (courtesy of Vosper Thornycroft (UK) Ltd.) (b) Computer simulation of the temperature distribution of the cylindrical section under hydrocarbon fire curve conditions. The cold face temperature, defined at the composite/steel interface, remains below 160°C for up to 60 minutes. (Intermediate curves are inter-laminar temperatures).

CONCLUSIONS

We have attempted to show in this paper that, despite their combustibility, organic matrix composites have considerable potential for use in large load-bearing structures which may be subject to fire. When used in sufficiently thick sections these materials are capable of withstanding severe temperatures and ablative effects by virtue of the endothermic nature of the resin decomposition process.

The thermal response of composite systems subjected to severe hydrocarbon fire conditions can be accurately predicted using an experimentally validated thermal model which provides basic data for performance based design.

Composite materials have already found application as passive fire protection for metallic structures and it is recognised that composite structures will outperform unprotected metallic structures under many severe fire conditions.

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